

Reasons for Land Transformation in Rurban Zone around Hyderabad City

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ABSTRACT

In recent years, cities in the less developed parts of the world have experienced rapid aerial expansion in the wake of phenomenal growth in population. Rural to migration has played significance role in urban growth in such countries. Large and cities in the developing countries are experiencing a constant high rate of growth in their populations and as a result, many of them are undergoing unplanned or uncontrolled expansion of settlement at the densely populated sites are in the fringes. In this paper I am presenting the reasons of land transformation in rurban zone around Hyderabad city. A lot of reasons is there but most important one is Urbanisation.

Keywords: *Aerial expansion, Migration, Rurban, Urbanization, Fringes, Settlement.*

INTRODUCTION

The Land Transformation is a land use forecasting model as well as a tool that can be used to examine the spatial and temporal aspects of driving forces of land use change. The world has seen development and growth of urban areas at a very fast pace. Currently it is, estimated nearly half of the world population lives in rural areas and half of the people lives in urban areas. Even in Telangana Rural people lives in 62% while urban people lives in 38%. These 62% of people major occupation is agriculture. These people lives is associated rural areas. I have been conducted the survey in Rurban zone around Hyderabad city especially some selected villages in Rangareddy district.

More developed countries are much more urbanized than less developed countries. The level of

urbanization refer to the proportion of people living in towns and cities, the process of urbanization is generally considered as a manifestation of socio-economic development cultural transformation in an area. All over the world, cities and towns are expanding through both natural increase and migration of people from countryside. Urbanization occurs because people move from rural areas to urban areas. The pace of urbanization is more rapid when the economy of the country is in the developing stage. Many of the less developed countries going or passing through this stage.

Urbanisation often occurs in the form of aerial expansion. This would mean encroachment on agriculture land monitoring and documenting is that the first step in addressing issue of global land use and land cover. Land use and land cover scenario in India has undergone is a radical change since in the introduction of New economic policy in early 1990 and these changes involves a series of complex interaction between biophysical and socio-economic variables.

OBJECTIVES

The main objective is to control the land transformation and stimulate local economic development, Enhance basic services and to create well planned Rurban zone around Hyderabad city especially in surrounding villages of Rangareddy, Mahabubnagar, Medhak, Nalgonda districts .

METHODOLOGY

The study focuses this area’s primary and secondary information collected from Based on the socio economic survey various books, magazines, national and international journals, government reports, publication from various websites focuses on the concept of Land transformation.

STUDY AREA

Hyderabad it’s surrounding area.

CURRENT SCENARIO OF LAND TRANSFORMATION IN RURBAN ZONE AROUND HYDERABAD CITY

S.No.	1990	2015	Big farmers (>4Ha)	Medium farmers (2-4Ha)	Small farmers (1-2Ha)	Marginal farmers (<1-Ha)
1	Big farmers (>4Ha)		They are changed into medium farmers			
2	Medium farmers (2-4Ha)			They are changed into small farmers		
3	Small farmers (1-2Ha)				They are changed into marginal farmers	
4	Marginal farmers (<1-Ha)					They are changed into Land less.

Source: Based on survey

SOIL TYPES IN RURBAN ZONE AROUND HYDERABAD CITY

Majorly two types of soils there in around Hyderabad city. These are

1. Red soils
2. Black soils

S.No.	Available soil type	Percentage
1.	Red soil	85%
2.	Black soil	10%
3.	Others	5%

Source: Based on survey

REASONS FOR LAND TRANSFORMATION

➤ **Urbanisation**

Urbanization refers to the population shift from rural to urban areas, "the gradual increase in the proportion of people living in urban areas", and the ways in which each society adapts to the change. Urbanisation is an increase in the number of people living in towns and cities. Urbanisation occurs mainly because people move from rural areas to urban areas and it results in growth in the size of the urban population and the extent of urban areas. This is the major reason for land transformation.

➤ **Rural- Urban fringe**

The rural-urban fringe, also known as the outskirts or the urban hinterland, can be described as the "landscape interface between town and country", or also as the transition zone where urban and rural uses mix and often clash.

➤ **Rural- Urban continuum**

Rural-urban continuum, the merging of town and country, a term used in recognition of the fact that in general there is rarely, either physically or socially, a sharp division, a clearly marked boundary between the two, with one part of the population wholly urban, the other wholly rural.

➤ **Real estate business**

Now a days Real estate business has great demand this is the reason for which the farmers are selling their lands for more money.

➤ **City expansion**

In current scenario cities are expanding to meet the needs of growing population, thus the nearby areas around city are also expanding.

➤ **Due to farmers daughter's marriage**

Generally the farmers does not possess money, if they do on their children's marriage they sell their land.

➤ **Less productivity due to pollution**

Especially in near urban zone the pollution is very high that is the one of the main reason for decrease the productivity then they are saw two or three years after sell their land.

➤ **Migration (Rural to Urban)**

It is regular phenomena to Rural to Urban migration due to work, education, health purpose etc.

➤ **In cities lack of labours**

Now a days a very huge building construction are there in cities and lot of formers to participate in that type of work and finally there are migrated to urban areas. Ex. KPHB(KUKATPALLY HOUSING BOARD) Colony.

➤ **Allied activities of Agriculture**

The allied activities like animal husbandry creating huge demand in the cities in the fields of Milk and Meat industry. Cities near areas like Ex. NADHARGUL, GURRAM GUDA. This village produces huge amount of milk and supplies to the city. Some villages merges into GHMC(Greater Hyderabad Municipal corporation)

Recently Telangana government has merged the new villages into GHMC, which is increasing the value of land of particular merged villages. Ex. KOTWALGUDA, SATHAM RAI.

SOLUTIONS

If we are in a state of overshoot, here are three ways to bring the human impact on Earth back to sustainability:

1. Reduce demand. Demand can be reduced by improving building insulation or mandating energy-efficient vehicles and appliances. Recycling reduces demand for primary materials. Tempering our impulse to buy things that we don't really need or of which we will soon tire also reduces demand.

2. Develop technological solutions. Existing technology can mitigate our impact. Adoption of efficient building and farming practices limits degradation, and ecological restoration can partially reverse it. Technological breakthroughs are also possible. Simon (1996) argued that a larger population increases the likelihood of spawning the brain power needed to achieve such breakthroughs. But without well-fed bodies, brains don't function well.

3. Reduce the population. Increasing the availability of health care, education, and micro financing, particularly for women in developing countries, reduces fertility. Reduced fertility reduces poverty, because available resources are distributed among fewer people. Couples worldwide can be urged to have only two children and to delay having them so there will be fewer people on Earth at any one time. These steps would first slow population growth and then lead to a long-term decline.

CONCLUSION

The above stated reasons like rural urban fringe, allied activities of agriculture and the source of financial income in the urban areas has uplifted the demand for more natural resources like land and water also the

manpower. Thus the cities are fastly expanding their hinterland which has a greater impact on the development of the hinterland of thee big cities.

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